

UNESCO AND SCHOOL BULLYING: PROBLEMS
AND SOLUTIONS

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“Bullying is a hidden process. Everyone knows about its existence, and when faced with its manifestations, everyone tries to do something. However, no one knows how much bullying-related suffering schoolchildren experience every day.”

David A. Lane

Abstract. The article, based on factual material around the world and Uzbekistan, attempts to highlight one of the pressing problems of modern schools - the problem of bullying and cyberbullying. It is common knowledge that violence and bullying in schools has become a global problem. According to UNESCO, today 34% of students aged 11-13 were bullied within a month, while 8% of schoolchildren admitted that this happened every day, sometimes even leading to fatal consequences. Due to daily bullying from classmates, some students do not want to go to class, withdraw into themselves, become irritable and passive, begin to fall behind in their studies, and sometimes even drop out of school. Considering the scale of bullying in school and its dangerous consequences for children, UNESCO, starting from 2020, officially declared the first Thursday of November as the International Day against Violence and Harassment in School Environments, recognizing violence in all its forms as a violation of the rights of children and adolescents to education, health and well-being . Activities on this day draw people's attention to global awareness of this dangerous social phenomenon. The purpose of the presented article is to conduct an analytical review of the problem

of bullying in school based on empirical data from large-scale foreign national and cross-cultural studies.

Key words: bullying at school, school bullying, cyberbullying, UNESCO, International Day, children's rights.

Introduction. The relevance of research.

According to the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, school bullying is the most common manifestation of aggression and cruelty among children and adolescents, undermining their right to education. UNESCO considers the key objectives of work in this area to be: eliminating violence and bullying in schools, including gender-based violence and preventing discrimination on the basis of health and gender against students and teachers. UNESCO pays serious attention to combating violence and bullying in school, conducting global awareness-raising campaigns, developing baseline indicators, coordinating and strengthening international cooperation [8].

In the UNESCO report “What's behind the numbers? Ending School Violence and Bullying”, presented to the World Education Forum 2019 in London in support of the Safe to Learn campaign, noted that violence and bullying in school affects both female and male students and is a serious global problem. UNESCO's new report, Reimagining Our Future Together: A New Social Contract for Education (10 November 2021), emphasizes that schools must be a pillar of social inclusion, equality and individual and collective well-being. Their work also needs to be reimagined to better help transform our world towards a more just, equitable and sustainable future. Schools must model the future we strive for, ensuring human rights and setting an example for sustainable development and carbon neutrality [12]. As UNESCO Assistant Director-General for Education, Ms Stefania Giannini, noted: “Through a combination of strong political leadership and other factors such as preparation, collaboration, reporting and monitoring, we can dispel the climate of fear caused by violence and intimidation in schools. All

children and young people have the right to a safe, inclusive and effective educational environment [7].

Presentation of the main research material.

Research results under the auspices of UNESCO and other international organizations show that bullying and cyberbullying have long-term negative effects on the health and well-being of both victims of bullying and the aggressors and witnesses themselves. They become accustomed to physical and psychological violence and, as a rule, reproduce learned behavior strategies in adulthood, resorting to bullying at work and in the family. Schoolchildren who systematically experience bullying are subsequently more prone to aggression, violence, alcohol abuse and the use of psychotropic substances. Bullying can provoke mental disorders of varying severity, as well as psychosomatic diseases, and can cause school shooting (an armed attack by a student on schoolchildren inside an educational institution). From the beginning of 2017 to January 2018, 13 incidents of attacks or the use of weapons in Russian schools were recorded. 71% of attackers are victims of prolonged and severe bullying [2].

The UNESCO report, *No Child Left Behind: A Global Report on Boys' Exclusion from Education* (April 2022), draws attention to a global phenomenon: harsh discipline, corporal punishment and other forms of violence in school, gendered norms and expectations, and other factors prevent boys from achieving academic success. It is because of these reasons that the number of truants and dropouts is increasing [19].

The 2018 HBSC (Health Behavior in SchoolAged Children Study) quadrennial report found the incidence of bullying among schoolchildren in more than 40 countries in North America and Europe aged 11, 13 and 15 years to be 10%, with a range of 2% (Iceland) to 27.5% (Lithuania). The share of victims of bullying among Russian schoolchildren in 2018 was 15.7% [2a]. There are no data for Uzbekistan.

One in two pupils between the ages of 13 and 15 – approximately 150 million children – experience peer violence in or around schools. A report by the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) entitled "Everyday Lesson: STOP Violence in Schools" highlights that bullying and physical violence by peers are common practices in schools around the world, and so-called "bullying" on the Internet has become an epidemic. UNICEF Executive Director Henrietta Fore, presenting the new report, said: "Education is the most important component of building a peaceful and safe society, but millions of children in different parts of the world do not feel safe in schools," "every day, somewhere, children get into fights, they are forced to join various groups and are harassed, including on social networks. Many girls and boys experience sexual abuse. This vicious phenomenon negatively affects children's academic performance, and in the long term can result in depression, the development of anxiety syndrome and even suicide." "Violence is an indelible trauma that no child in the world should experience" [6].

The need to study bullying is explained by its widespread prevalence in society, especially among children and adolescents, and the numerous negative consequences for both its victims and the psychological health of society. The problem of bullying is being actively studied at the international level. School bullying began to be actively researched in the 1970-80s. last century in the Scandinavian countries. In 2009-2010, as part of the research project E&U&OpNpe II, conducted in 26 European countries, including Russia, it was revealed that every fifth teenager in Europe (19%) and every fourth in Russia (23%) were victims of offline bullying and online. On average in Europe, 6% of teenagers have been bullied online in the last 12 months; in Russia this figure was 10%. The proportion of teenagers who experienced online bullying in Europe varied from country to country. For example, the maximum figure was in Estonia - 14%, and the minimum in Italy - 2%. In 2013-2014. The HBSC (Health Behavior In School-Aged Children) organization, in collaboration with the World Health Organization (WHO), conducted a large-scale study (220,000 schoolchildren),

which collected data in 42 European countries, including Russia and North America. The study was conducted among 11-, 13- and 15-year-old adolescents. The results showed that on average across Europe, 3% of children of each age surveyed had been cyberbullied through text messages 2-3 times in the last month. In a large-scale review of 80 studies conducted at the beginning of the second millennium, which analyzed the incidence of cyberbullying among students aged 12-18, it was found that 15% of respondents were victims of cyberbullying. According to research by the National Center for Educational Statistics conducted in 2015 schools in the country during the 2013-14 school year, 10.8% of adolescents aged 12 to 18 experienced cyberbullying during the school year. The Cyberbullying Research Center in the USA conducted 10 unique studies on a sample of over 20,000 middle and high school students in 2007-2016. It has been found that, on average, about 28% of students have been victims of cyberbullying at some point in their lives [14]. In 2019, UNICEF conducted an anonymous survey in which 170 thousand young people aged 13 to 24 years old from 30 countries took part. More than a third of respondents claim that they have encountered manifestations of bullying on social networks, and every fifth respondent missed classes due to bullying from classmates. According to a 2017 report by Ofcom, one in eight children aged 12 to 15 have experienced bullying and threats from strangers online. According to the Suffolk Cybersurvey report (2016), the peak impact of cyberbullying occurs among adolescents aged 14 to 16 [3]. Research has shown that on average 7 out of 10 young people have been bullied online at some point in their lives [17].

Research results have shown that any child can become a victim of bullying, regardless of age, gender and nationality. Both girls and boys become victims of cyberbullying almost equally. Among those surveyed, 60% of girls and 59% of boys experienced at least one type of cyberbullying. Both of them regularly face abusive behavior, but it is girls who more often become victims of the spread of rumors and insults, with threats of physical harm. Girls (29%) are more likely to

receive unwanted explicit photos than boys (20%) [3]. Rates of cyberbullying vary from country to country. According to one estimate, 10-20% of young people are bullied during their school years, and from 5 to 15% of teenagers themselves bully others. However, many children who are exposed to this type of violence experience subsequent repeated and persistent victimization. A review by Robert S. Tokunaga found that approximately 20–40% of young people have experienced cyberbullying at least once in their lives [11].

Any bullying is dangerous for the psychological health of the victims. Research shows that bullying often leads children and adolescents to depression and other disorders, low self-esteem, and isolation. They think about suicide more often, and sometimes it actually comes to suicide [4].

In a study by K.J. Mitchell and L.M. Jones, about 23% of the adolescents surveyed reported that during the past month they had been victims of various forms of bullying (cyber, hidden, physical and verbal forms), with 25.6% of these victims indicating that they were subjected to this in the Internet space, 50.3% that were victims of all four forms of violence. According to another study, depending on the country of residence, from 5 to 20% of children become victims of cyberbullying. M. van Geel, P. Vedder, and D. Tanilon conducted a meta-analysis of studies on the relationship between peer victimization, adolescent suicidal ideation, and suicide attempts. The scientometric databases Ovid MEDLINE, PsycINFO and Web of Science were searched for relevant articles from 1910 to 2013. The review included those studies that reported the magnitude of the correlation between peer victimization and suicidal ideation or suicide attempts in children and adolescents. Of the 491 studies identified, 34 of them (with a total of 284,375 respondents) showed associations between peer victimization and suicidal ideation. Nine studies (total of 70,102 subjects) reported such an association. It was found that victimization of children and adolescents often leads to both suicidal ideation (2.23 times increase in probability compared to non-victimized subjects) and suicide attempts (2.55 times increase). In general, peer victimization is a risk factor

for suicidal ideation and attempts for children and adolescents. Approximately 20% of adolescents have seriously considered suicide, and 5% to 8% of adolescents in the United States attempt suicide within a year; Overall, suicide is one of the most common causes of death among adolescents worldwide [11].

A study of the prevalence and determinants of self-reported suicidal ideation and attempts among younger (13–15 years) and older adolescents (16–17 years) in 90 countries covered by the Global School Health Survey (GSHS) from 2003 to 2017 shows that being bullied or not having close friends was associated with suicidal ideation in girls aged 13–15 and 16–17 years, respectively [15]. Among all boys, involvement in a fight and lack of close friends were associated with suicidal ideation, with the addition of serious trauma in boys 13–15 years of age [6].

The victim of bullying stops trusting others and does not know who to turn to for support and protection. A student who is being bullied feels increasingly lonely, stress increases, and emotional reactions can become very violent [2]. Common to all younger adolescents was the association of suicide attempts with bullying and serious trauma. Among boys, the absence of close friends was an additional indicator of a suicide attempt. A lack of close friends has been associated with suicide attempts in older adolescents, as well as bullying in older girls and serious injury in older boys [15]. Bullying in the form of boycott, practiced over a long period of time, is the most common cause of suicide [2].

Recognizing that bullying in schools and on the Internet is one of the most serious problems of the modern educational system, a gross violation of the rights of children and adolescents to education, health and well-being, the need to ensure a safe and positive educational environment in 2019, UNESCO Member States decided to 2020 year, the first Thursday of November to declare a new “International Day against School Violence and Bullying and Cyberbullying”. According to the UNESCO report “What's behind the numbers? Eliminating Violence and Bullying in School” (2019) Violence and bullying of children and youth at school, as well as teachers and students, by their own classmates is a

serious problem on a global scale. Bullying has a serious negative impact on children's mental health, quality of life and academic performance. Children who are frequently bullied are almost three times more likely to feel like outsiders at school. They are also more than twice as likely to skip school compared to children who are not bullied as often. The academic performance of such children is worse than that of their peers. In addition, they are more likely to drop out of school after graduating from high school [13].

A study conducted by UNESCO in 144 countries confirms this and calls into question the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process; Moreover, it poses a danger to the lives of children and threatens their future. In Europe and North America, school bullying is expressed mainly in psychological pressure, and every tenth student is subject to cyberbullying. In other parts of the world, physical violence comes first, sexual violence comes second. 68 countries around the world still allow physical punishment in schools [18].

The Internet and modern electronic devices have made possible the widespread spread of cyberbullying among students in schools, colleges and universities in various forms: spreading rumors, ridiculing and/or humiliating another, posting intimate photographs or videos of the victim without his or her consent, often distorting personal data and information , remaining anonymous and unpunished. Victims have virtually no opportunity to avoid insults and humiliation in the online space, and many are in a constant state of stress and anxiety because of this. Every third victim of bullying began to self-harm as a result, and every tenth attempted suicide [17]. 26% of those who were bullied thought about suicide, 25% self-harmed, 14% had an eating disorder, 37% were depressed, and 9% used alcohol or drugs [14]. Research results consistently show that approximately every second teenager who experiences bullying does not tell anyone about it out of fear, embarrassment or lack of faith in the effectiveness of support systems. In 2019, Mail.ru Group conducted a study on online bullying, dedicated to the Day against Cyberbullying, which is celebrated on November 11. According to the study, 58%

of Russians have experienced bullying online. Moreover, about 76% of teenagers do not tell their parents about bullying [4].

The most toxic social network, according to research, is Instagram. About 42% of respondents experienced cyberbullying and harassment on this platform [3]. After analyzing 19 million tweets over a four-year period, the authors of a joint report by anti-bullying charity Ditch the Label and social media monitoring company Brandwatch counted almost 5 million incidents of misogyny on Twitter alone. Fifty-two percent of misogynistic comments were made by women themselves, usually making comments about the appearance, intelligence, and sexual preferences of other women. The report found 7.7 million incidents of racism, 390,296 acts of homophobia and 19,348 transphobic statements found on Twitter. Because the report's authors analyzed only public data, when extrapolating their findings to the entire Internet, taking into account both public and private communication channels, the amount of hate speech online is staggering [17]. A review of 159 studies by Portuguese researchers found that one-year cyberbullying prevalence rates ranged from 3.0% to 39.0%, and cyberbullying victimization rates ranged from 1.0% to 61.1%. In an EU Kids Online study of more than 25,000 young people aged 9 to 16 years from 25 European countries, 19% of children reported cyberbullying. In Belgium, a third of students indicated that they had been victims of cyberbullying, and approximately one fifth of students surveyed reported that they had participated in cyberbullying. A study by Italian scientists reported that about 20-22% of Italian teenagers said they had been a victim of cyberbullying at least once. D. Nikolaou states the influence of cyberbullying on the suicidal behavior of young people (both on thoughts of suicide and suicide attempts), with girls suffering more from cyberbullying, but men more often take action, and their attempts are significantly more often accompanied by completed suicides. Twenty-seven studies provided cyberbullying prevalence rates ranging from 5.3% to 66.2% (median = 11.7%). Across seven studies, victimization rates ranged from 2.3 to 20.4% (median = 8.6%) [10]. All popular social networks have

already realized the scale of the problem of cyberbullying. Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, VKontakte and other platforms have tools that will help limit interaction with unwanted users, report violations of the law and harassment [15a].

The problem of cyber violence has long been an issue for international organizations, in particular UNICEF. Many years ago they launched a youth manifesto to end violence in schools, which was presented to ministers at the World Education Forum in January 2019. It emphasizes: “Equality is at the core of promoting diversity and tolerance in schools. Equality must be taught and demonstrated in the home and reinforced in schools. We must recognize that we are all equal.” “Our differences, including culture, gender, identity, disability, sexual orientation, nationality, race, ethnicity, migration status and religion, make us unique and should be celebrated rather than divided.” “...schools, in collaboration with parents, peers and society at large must care for, support and protect all students – those who are exposed to violence and those who engage in violent behavior.” “We demand protection and prevention of all forms and levels of violence in schools, which must be governed by clear rules, regulations and action plans that enable reform and safe learning environments for all.”[5]

In Uzbekistan, the issue of school bullying began to be discussed in December 2019, when the Ministry of Public Education and UNESCO began implementing a joint project to prevent bullying in schools in Uzbekistan. However, in our country, research and statistics on bullying are still lacking. The expressions “school violence”, “bullying” and “bullying” are not mentioned in any legislative act of the country [16].

On April 26, 2022, a press conference was held at the National Press Center on the topic “Working with violence against children in the public education system.” Munir Mammadzade, UNICEF representative in Uzbekistan, said he was pleased with the work being carried out jointly with the Ministry of Public Education. At the same time, in order to protect children from violence, he

announced the launch of a “hotline” together with the Republican Diagnostic Center [7a].

Surveys of adolescents in many countries conducted in 2019 by UNICEF show that bullying is a fairly common form of extremism in the modern world of youth. When asked “Have you ever feared violence in or around your school?” over a million young people from 160 countries: 2 in 3 said they were concerned about violence in and around schools [9].

Violence in schools can have serious long-term consequences for children's lives, their futures and the future of the communities in which they live. Let us cite, as an example, several anonymous stories from teenagers in Uzbekistan about bullying. Story No. 1: “In grade 6-7, I was very fat, and all my classmates bullied me. It got to the point that they wouldn't let me into class, they would push me into men's restrooms and wouldn't let me out, and they would call me names in public. When the teacher moved us, my classmates did not want to sit with me. “I don't want to sit with a pig,” they said. I was stressed and depressed because no one wanted to be friends with me or hang out with me simply because of my weight and appearance. I didn't go to school for a year and switched to homeschooling. During this time, I lost weight and became “more or less”, but I transferred to another school and started a new life.” Story No. 2: “I was called a “hanger”, a “toothpick” and other “names”, but I perfectly understood and knew what “bullying” was during my school years, and how people all over the world suffer from it.” Story No. 3: “At school I was severely bullied because I was thin... In the 6th grade, bullying from school students continued, only now high school students joined in and shouted to my face that I was “flat.” I remember I came and cried a lot, but at the same time I no longer told my parents about the humiliation. After some time, I simply stopped paying attention to the name-calling [16].

Any violence, whether on the Internet or in real life, causes enormous damage to the mental and physical health of young people and provokes more and more attacks of stress [17]. Numerous studies conducted in different parts of the

world confirm the urgent need to develop programs aimed at preventing adolescents and young people from encountering unpleasant, hostile and aggressive situations in the online space, as well as programs aimed at coping with situations of cyberbullying [14]. As noted by Academician of the Russian Academy of Education, one of the leading experts in the field of age-related physiology M.M. Bezrukikh in an interview published in “News of Education” on January 24, 2023, in modern “schools there is a lot of rudeness, impatience, misunderstanding, and aggression. All these are stressful situations that interfere with the child’s development, his learning, and create the ground for physical and mental health problems. These disorders persist throughout life, preventing them from living and working actively and successfully. Adults should know this and remember their responsibility. Perhaps we need to talk about this more and more often, teach parents, help them. Then it will be easier for the children” [1].

Preventing violence among teenagers online and offline is an important area of UNESCO activity: an unhealthy psychological climate in the school community not only negatively affects the academic performance, motivation and emotional state of students, but also often becomes a factor that directly affects the health and well-being of young children [4]. Commitment to providing safe and positive school and classroom environments, effective reporting and monitoring systems for school violence and bullying, evidence-based programs and policies, teacher training and support, providing support and assistance to affected students, empowering and empowering students led to a decrease in the number of fights or physical attacks in 71 countries and territories surveyed [7].

Conclusions.

Teachers have a critical role to play in solving the problem of bullying in school. Highly appreciating the significance of their participation, UNESCO pays serious attention to the implementation of initiatives for the initial training and professional development of teachers in order to strengthen their skills and knowledge in countering violence and bullying in school [8]. This requires paying

serious attention to the training of teachers and staff of educational institutions on prevention issues and counteracting cases of violence and bullying, involving parents and the local community in solving this problem, providing timely assistance to victims of bullying and violence. UNESCO Director-General Audrey Azoulay, in his message on the occasion of the International Day against Violence and Bullying in Schools (2022), notes that “teachers are at the forefront of the fight against bullying in school and they are the ones who feel the direct consequences of this problem: three out of five Teachers surveyed in a UNESCO study said that the violence they experience in the classroom has a negative impact on their daily work.”[8] “We must teach children how to properly use the Internet and information technology - set privacy settings, learn to block unwanted content, and be careful when posting their personal information in the public domain. It is not the mobile phone or the Internet that is the problem, but their irresponsible and inattentive use” [4]. On April 21, the UNESCO Institute for Information Technologies in Education (UNESCO IITE) took part in a special project of the online publication Mel.fm at MIEF 2018 - the lecture “Social networks for the benefit of schools.” At this platform, experts from the world of education and the digital environment spoke about the changes that pedagogical practice is undergoing under the influence of the Internet and new media, and discussed how unresolved problems and “blank spots” that appear in the process of transforming the educational process to meet the needs of and demands of the digital natives generation [4]. One of these “spots” is cyberbullying.

According to long-term observations of researchers, often the reason for children’s cruel behavior and treatment of other students is anger, envy, desire for revenge, thirst for popularity and increasing authority. It is impossible to cope with the facts of violence at school with single measures (training, lecture, parent-teacher meeting, calling to the director). Public repentance and threats of expulsion from school do not work. Systematic work is required to identify problematic

situations and measures to support and protect those children who find themselves under pressure [2].

1. It is important when working with the class to explain to students: what is happening is violence. Each child should rate their participation in bullying on a scale from 1 to 10.
2. You need to ask the guys to imagine themselves in the place of the victim, without arousing pity for the victim. Discuss with the class and accept the new rules by which the group will now interact. Write these rules down and post them in a visible place in the classroom.
3. Voice that this phenomenon is unacceptable at school. Keep a daily record or chart of positive changes in the group so that it is clear in which direction the group is moving.
4. Organize a number of events and build interaction so that each child can show their talent, feel useful to the class and feel valuable and needed [16].

Children should not be afraid to go to school. On the new International Day against Violence and Bullying in Schools, including Cyberbullying, UNESCO calls on all countries, organizations and stakeholders to unite towards a common goal - to make schools free from fear and violence, and the Internet free from all forms of cyberbullying [4] .

It is necessary to increase attention to countering violence and bullying in school, to eradicate the causes of their occurrence, and to create an atmosphere of a culture of mutual respect, understanding and friendship in any educational institution. For as one of the most outstanding philosophers of antiquity, Cicero, said: There is nothing better and more pleasant in the world than friendship; excluding friendship from life is the same as depriving the world of sunlight.

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